

The Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative
A Checklist of the Lichens on Nantucket Island.
Town of Nantucket, Nantucket County, MA, USA
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Abstract: Collections made at 14 sites on Nantucket Island during the 2006 and 2007 NBI Weeks have added 53 species in 33 genera to the 2004 lichen list of 89 species in 37 genera. In all 21 genera have been added to the historical list for the island, increasing the number of genera to 61 and the species list to 148 species. Five species, *Bacidia helicospora*, *Pyrrhospora querneae*, *Physcia pumilior*, *Cladonia abbreviatula* and *Usnea cornuta* appear to be new records for Massachusetts. *Ramalina willeyi* is well established on the island as are other *Ramalinas* thought to be uncommon in the region, such as *Usnea mutabilis*, *Ramalina americana* and *Ramalina farinacea*. *Skyttea radiatilis* and *Mycoglaena* sp. (saprophytic fungi related to lichens and lichenicolous fungi) and *Naetrocymbe punctiformis*, a lichenicolous fungus, are reported for the island.

This lichen inventory work is a continuation of the work started during the 2004 NBI Week. Different lichen assemblages develop in different plant communities and on different substrates. The aim of this work was to survey habitats not examined in 2004 to document the lichen diversity in diverse sites and to attempt to document lichen species recorded for Nantucket Island in The Vascular and Non-Vascular Flora of Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands by Sorries and Dunwiddie in 1996.

Scope of the Inventory and Methods

The localities of the sites surveyed in 2006-2007 are listed below. Note that some sites were quick stops that afforded limited sampling while at others two hours were spent sampling. Substrates examined for lichens include soil, rocks, pebbles, duff, shells, bones, wood, and 13 species of woody plants (*Rosa rugosa*, *Quercus ilicifolia*, *Quercus alba*, *Pinus rigida*, *Juniperus virginiana*, *Myrica pensylvanica*, *Prunus maritima*, *Acer rubrum*, *Vaccinium corymbosum*, *Nyssa sylvatica*, *Rhododendron viscosum*, apple trees and viburnum).

Chemical spot tests were used in the identification of lichens. Thin layer chromatography was done on four species of *Usnea* with Francis Anderson.

Lichen records are entered into a Microsoft Excel database that can be searched by species, site localities, voucher numbers and substrates colonized.

Voucher collections will be placed in the Maria Mitchell Association Museum of Natural History and the Farlow Herbarium (FH) at Harvard University.

The Localities for the 2006 and 2007 NBI Weeks Lichen Inventory work.

2006 Sites:

1. Middle Moors: Scrub Oak Barrens

Plot center established at N41° 16.563' W069° 59.37'. Plot with a 34.7m radius, (0.378 ha) surveyed for lichens for 2 hours. Lichens collected off scrub oak (*Quercus ilicifolia*) bark (N41° 16.552' W069° 59.329), black huckleberry bark (*Gaylussacia baccata*) (N41° 16.546' W069° 59.350') and from the soil and pebbles on the plot, especially at N41° 16.542' W069° 59.357'. 8/30/2006

2. The Middle Moors: Scrub Oak Barrens

Lichens collected off the bark of a single partially burnt mature *Quercus ilicifolia* in a scrub oak thicket. N41° 16.555' W069° 59.421' 8/31/2006

3. Serengeti: *Pinus rigida* bark and cones.

N41° 15.961' W070° 01.814'. Random sampling of less than 10 branches and woody cones of *Pinus rigida* in the Serengeti. Quick stops while tiger beetle traps were being checked. 8/31/2006.

4. Sanford Farm: Grassland and Woody Thicket.

- A. Grassy field site of approximately ¼ of a 114' plot. Collections made off soil, pebbles, one buried rock and dried rabbit pellets.
Plot center: N41° 16.359' W070° 08.446' 8/31/2006
- B. Bark of edge tree, black cherry (*Prunus serotina*) and dead branches of bayberry (*Myrica pensylvanica*) as well as soil lichens on hill adjacent to parking lot. N41° 16.322' W070° 08.526' 8/31/2006
- C. Wooded area at edge of grassy field (A). Only bark of *Amelanchier* checked. N41° 16.322' W070° 08.526' 9/2/2006

5. Eel Point # 2 Coastal Dune:

Plot center established at N41° 17.615' W070° 11.734' (N4572069.287 E3992112.359) Plot with a 34.7m radius, (0.378 ha) surveyed for lichens for 2 hours. Lichens collected off sand, weathered wood, beachgrass (*Ammophila breviligulata*) stubble, beach rose (*Rosa rugosa*) and bayberry (*Myrica pensylvanica*) and weathered seashells. 8/31/2006

6. Wyer's Point: Dune and Coastal Shrubland.

Plot center established at N41° 20.068' W070° 02.044' (N4576400.630 E 413474.075) Plot with a 34.7m radius, (0.378 ha) surveyed for lichens for 2 hours. Lichens collected off the bark of two large windblown maritime cedars (*Juniperus virginiana*), dead stems of bayberry (*Myrica pensylvanica*), an (off plot) low growing beach plum (*Prunus maritima*), dried bird bones and sea shells, sand and weathered wood. Back protected area of plot behind shrubs N 41° 20.054' W070° 02.031'. 9/01/2006

7. The Cedars: Maritime Cedar Forest.

Entered at site of 4 metal posts on the south side of the road, N41° 21.704' W 070° 01.149'. Surveyed lichens along an approximately 175m line that ran from N41° 21.669' W 070° 01.169' to N 41° 21.666' W070° 01.214'. Collected lichens off two maritime cedars (*Juniperus virginiana*) and sand. Also collected *Usnea trichodea* off *J. virginiana* at edge of cross road N 41° 21.701' W070° 01.252'.
9/2/2006

8. Coskata Woods:

A rapid walk from the trail out to the point. Only collected lichens off oak (*Quercus*) and sassafras (*Sassafras albidum*) at N41° 20.792' W070° 01.130'. Visibility limited by low light. N 4577827.317 E 415025.005 9/2/2006

9. Random sites in the Town of Nantucket:

- a. Tree on Milk St.-bark litter collected off the ground.
N 41° 16.897' W070° 06.195'. 8/30/06
- b. Maria Mitchell Hinchman House rock wall and pond rocks- not all species collected. Entered with collection numbers for distribution records.
N 41° 21.660' W070° 00.213'. 9/1/06
- c. House shingles –confirmation granules scratched off surface of shingles
N 41° 21.660' W070° 00.123'. 9/1/06

10. Lost Farm Wildlife Sanctuary, The Massachusetts Audobon Society Property:

A Pitch Pine Forest N41° 15.978' W070° 08.028'
After a class lichens were collected off downed *Pinus rigida* logs and stumps, an oak tree, viburnum and soil. During a second short stop the focus was on the large *Usneas* and the soil *Cladonias*. N41° 16.051' W070° 08.141' 9/12/06

11. Quaisse: Mesic Forest/Dry Oak Forest

The bark of two red maples (*Acer rubrum*) (# 1 N41° 17.566' W070° 00.508'; # 2. N41° 17.560' W070° 00.504'), several oaks (*Quercus sp.*), branches of high bush blueberry (*Vaccinium corymbosum*), swamp azalea (*Rhododendron viscosum*), and soil. 9/11/2006

12. Lost Forest: Mesic Forest

This stop was a very quick look-and-see. *Phaeophyscia rubropulchra* on red maple (*Acer rubrum*) and lignicolous logs. 9/11/2006

2007 Sites:

10. Lost Farm Wildlife Sanctuary, The Massachusetts Audobon Society Property:

A Pitch Pine Forest N41° 15.978' W070° 08.028' revisited. Ramalinas collected off mature *Myrica pensylvancia*. Pendent *Usneas* collected. Walk around trails away from the pitch pine. 9/23/2007

13. Family vegetable Garden with small orchard and a weathered deer fence:

Property of Mr. and Mrs. James V. Gross, 16 Margaret Way, Polpits.
N41° 18.494' W070° 00.084.' Corticolous and lignicolous collections made
off apple and pear trees and weathered fence. 9/23/2007

14. Urban: Old maples lining Chapel St., Sconset.

N41° 15.774' W069° 57.962.' *Ramalinas* abundant of tree trunks, a few
collections made. 9/23/2007

Results and Discussion

The collections made in 2006 and 2007 during the NBI Weeks added 53 species in 33 genera to the lichen records for Nantucket Island. The lichen diversity now stands at 148 species in 61 genera. Twenty-one genera have been added to the historical list. The diversity of lichens collected reflects the number of different habitats sampled, the number of different substrates checked for lichens and the time spent at some sites.

Anzia colpodes, *Lobaria pulmonaria* *Teloschistes chrysophthalmus* and *Trypethelium virens* have yet to be found on Nantucket. *Anzia colpodes* is an indicator of old-growth forests. It resembles the more common *Hypogymnia physodes* so it could be overlooked in the field. It is also a more northern species and not common to the southeastern plain (Hinds & Hinds 2007). *Lobaria pulmonaria* was last recorded for Nantucket in 1940. It was found on Tuckernuck in 2006 suggesting it might still be found on Nantucket. *Teloschistes chrysophthalmus*, a fruticose lichen that is very sensitive to low air quality, has not been reported for the island. *Trypethelium virens* is included in the historical record as colonizing *Ilex* bark. *Ilex* bark was not sampled in this survey. This species is common in New England and should occur on the island.

The crustose species *Pertusaria sulcata* and *Pyrrhospora querneae* collected off *Pinus rigida* bark, the foliose *Physcia pumilior* collected off *Quercus ilicifolia* and crustose *Bacidia helicospora* are all thought to be new records for Massachusetts (Greene 2008).

Of very special interest is the diversity and abundance of both *Usnea* and *Ramalina* species on Nantucket. Many of the species collected are thought to have been reduced by the loss of old-growth stands and low air quality in the New England area. *Ramalina willeyi*, *Ramalina americana* and *Ramalina farinacea* are quite common on the island. *Usnea cornuta* may be a new record for Massachusetts (Greene 2008). The size and fertility of *Usnea subscabrosa* and *Usnea trichodea* speaks to the age of the maritime red cedar forests and the pitch pines stands they grow in and to the quality of the air on the island. Nantucket island is truly a remarkable refugium for these two genera in southern New England.

Several of the sites already sampled merit return visits because time limited the substrates sampled. There remain specific substrates, such as intertidal rocks, that have yet to be sampled.

The number of new records for the island netted by the field work suggests that further sampling is still well worth doing.

The lichen records for Nantucket Island are listed the checklist below.

**A Checklist of the Lichens of Nantucket Island collected during
the 1st 2004 and the 2nd 2006 Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative
Nantucket Island, Town of Nantucket, Nantucket County, MA, USA**

Summary: The checklist includes 148 lichen species in 61 genera, 3 species of saprophytic fungi related to lichens or lichenicolous fungi (*) and 2 species of lichenicolous fungi (+). The additional 52 species (in 32 genera) made to the checklist in 2006 and 2007 are indicated with the symbol (•).

Collections were made June 1-3, 2004; August 30- 31 and September 1-2 and September 11-12, 2006; September 23-24, 2007.

Nomenclature follows Esslinger, T. L 2007. A cumulative checklist for the lichen-forming, lichenicolous and allied fungi of the continental United States and Canada. North Dakota State University: <http://www.ndsu.nodak.edu/instruct/chchlst/chchlst7.htm> (First posted 1 December 1997, Most Recent Update 2 April 2007), Fargo, North Dakota.

Key to checklist notations:

- * = lichenicolous fungi (parasites on living lichens)
- + = saprophytic fungi related to lichens or lichenicolous fungi
- = 2006 and 2007 additions to the Nantucket Island Flora

Acarospora fuscata (Schrader) Arnold (Kneiper, field id.)
Acarospora smaragdula (Wahlenb.) A. Massal
Amandinea millitaria (Tuck.) P. May & Sheard (Kneiper 4310, 4412)
Amandinea polyspora (Willey) E. Lay & P. May (Kneiper 1080)
Amandinea punctata (Hoffm.) Coppins & Scheid. (Kneiper 4353, 4423, 4424, 4494)
• *Anisomeridium bifforme* (Borrer) R. C. Harris (Kneiper 4394)
Arthonia caesia (Flotow) Körber
• *Arthonia quintaria* Nyl. (Kneiper 4291)
Aspicilia sp. (field id)
• *Bacidia helicospora* S. Ekman (Kneiper 4448)
Bacidia schweinitzii (Fr.ex E. Michener) A. Schneider
• *Bacidina egenula* (Nyl.) Vězda (Kneiper 4507)
Biatora helvola **Körber ex Hellbom**
Biatora vernalis (L.) Fr.
• *Bryoria furcellata* (Fr.) Brodo & D. Hawksw. (Kneiper 4314, 4315)
Buellia stillingiana J. Steiner (Kneiper 4338, 4398, 4541)
• *Calicium parvum* Tibell (Kneiper 4320, 4371)
Caloplaca citrina (Hoffm.) Th. Fr. (Kneiper 4518)
• *Caloplaca feracissima* H. Magn. (Kneiper 4506)
• *Caloplaca flavovirescens* (Wulfen) Dalla Torre & Sarnth. (Kneiper 4441)
Caloplaca holocarpa (Hoff. ex Ach.)

Candelaria concolor (Dickson) Stein
 • *Candelariella aurella* (Hoffm.) Zahlbr. (Kneiper 4512)
 • *Candelariella efflorescens* R. C. Harris & W. R. Buck (Kneiper 4519)
Candelariella vitellina (Hoff.) Müll. Arg.
Cetraria arenaria Kärnefelt (Kneiper 4295)
 • *Cladonia abbreviatula* G. Merr. (Kneiper 4311)
Cladonia arbuscula (Wallr.) Flotow (Kneiper 4377, 4395, 4409, 4420)
Cladonia boryi Tuck. (Kneiper 4297, 4383)
 • *Cladonia caespiticia* (Pers.) Flörke (Kneiper 4450)
 • *Cladonia cervicornis* subsp. *verticillata* (Hoffm.) Ahti (Kneiper 4499)
Cladonia chlorophaea (Flörke ex Sommerf.) Sprengel (Kneiper 4416)
Cladonia coniocraea (Flörke) Sprengel (Kneiper 4345, 4458)
 • *Cladonia crispata* (Ach.) Flotow var. *crispata* (Kneiper 4469, 4470)
Cladonia cristatella Tuck. (Kneiper 4324, 4326, 4384)
 • *Cladonia farinacea* (Vainio) A. Evans (Kneiper 4402, 4437)
Cladonia floerkeana (Fr.) Flörke (Kneiper 4381, 4389)
Cladonia furcata (Hudson) Schrader (Kneiper 4429)
Cladonia grayi G. Merr. ex Sandst. (Kneiper 4323)
 • *Cladonia humilis* (With.) J. R. Laundon (Kneiper 4495)
Cladonia incrassata Flörke (Kneiper 4319, 4333)
Cladonia macilenta Hoffm. (Kneiper 4296, 4400, 4436)
Cladonia macilenta var. *bacillaris* (Genth) Schaerer (Kneiper 5421)
Cladonia mitis Sandst. (Kneiper 4144, 4375)
 • *Cladonia ochrochlora* Flörke (Kneiper 4336, 4448)
 • *Cladonia parasitica* (Hoffm.) Hoffm. (Kneiper 4527, 4347)
Cladonia polycarpoides Nyl. (Kneiper 4299, 4433, 4435, 4438)
Cladonia ramulosa (With.) J. R. Laundon (Kneiper 4318)
Cladonia rangiferina (L.) F. H. Wigg. (Kneiper 4300, 4430, 4372, 4427)
 • *Cladonia scabriuscula* (Delise) Nyl. (Kneiper 4446)
Cladonia simulata Robbins
 • *Cladonia sobolescens* Nyl. ex Vainio (Kneiper 4386a)
Caldonia squamosa Hoffm.
 • *Cladonia stellaris* (Opiz) Pouzar & Vězda (Kneiper 4334, 4338)
Caldonia strepsilis (Ach.) Grognot
Cladonia submitis A. Evans (Kneiper 4380, 4387, 4408, 4418, 4432)
Cladonia subtenuis (Abbayes) Mattick (Kneiper 4373, 4374, 4378, 4388, 4420)
Cladonia terrae-novae Ahti (Kneiper 4386, 4396)
Cladonia uncialis (L.) F. H. Wigg. (Kneiper 4382)
Cliostomum griffithii (Sm.) Coppins (Kneiper 4317)
 • *Coenogonium pineti* (Ach.) ined. (Kneiper 4332, 4455)
Dibaeis baeomyces (L. F.) Rambold & Hertel (Kneiper 4301)
Dimelaena oreina (Ach.) Norman
 • *Evernia mesomorpha* Nyl. (Kneiper 4304)
Flavoparmelia baltimorensis (Gyelnik & Fóriss) Hale (Field id)
Flavoparmelia caperata (L.) Hale (Kneiper 4393)
Fuscidea arboricola Coppins & Tønsberg (Kneiper 4316)

Hypogymnia physodes (L.) Nyl. (Kneiper 4305, 4348)
Graphis scripta (L.) Ach.
Imshaugia aleurites (Ach.) S. F. Meyer (Kneiper 4327)
 • *Imshaugia placorodia* (Ach.) S. F. Meyer (Kneiper 4345, 4347)
 • *Lecania naegelia* (Hepp) Diederich & v. d. Boom (Kneiper 4459)
 • *Lecanora chlarotera* Nyl. *sensu lato* (Kneiper 4428)
 • *Lecanora crenulata* (Dicks.) Hook *sensu lato* (Kneiper 4523, 4524)
Lecanora dispersa Pers.Sommerf. (Kneiper 4406, 4439, 4517)
Lecanora hybocarpa (Tuck.) Brodo (Kneiper 4336, 4429)
Lecanora strobilina (Sprengel) Kieffer (Kneiper 4389, 4397, 4415)
Lecanora subpallens Zahlbr. (Kneiper 4339, 4454)
 • *Lepraria incana* (L.) Ach. (Kneiper 4355)
Lepraria lobificans Nyl. (Kneiper 4350, 4457, 4511)
Leptogium cyanescens (Rabenh.) Körber (Kneiper 4443)
Loxospora pustulata (Brodo & Culb.) R. C. Harris (Kneiper 4372, infecting 4452)
Melanelixia subaurifera (Nyl.) O. Blanco et al. (Kneiper 4308, 4392)
Micarea erratica (Körber) Hertel, Rambold & Pietschmann (Kneiper 4303)
 • *Micarea melaena* (Nyl) Hedl. (Kneiper 4328)
 • *Micarea prasina* Fr. (Kneiper 4331)
 • + *Mycocalicium subtile* (Pers.) Szatala (Kneiper 4520)
 • + *Mycoglaena* sp. (Kneiper 4398)
 • **Naetrocymbe punctiformis* (Pers.) R. C. Harris (Kneiper 4528)
 • *Ochrolechia africana* Vainio (Kneiper 4451)
Opographa atra Pers.
 • *Opographa niveoatra* (Borrer) J. R. Laundon (Kneiper 4445)
 • *Opographa viridis* (Pers. ex Ach.) Behlen & Desberger (Kneiper 4456)
Parmelia squarrosa Hale (Kneiper 4306)
Parmelia sulcata Taylor (Kneiper 4307)
Parmotrema chinense (Osbeck) Hale & Ahti (Kneiper 4479)
Parmotrema hypoleucinum (Steiner) Hale (Kneiper 4329, 4442)
Parmotrema hypotropum (Nyl.) Hale (Kneiper 4341,4417)
Parmotrema perforatum (Jacq.) A. Massal
 • *Parmotrema reticulatum* (Taylor) M. Choisy (Kneiper 4453)
Pertusaria amara (Ach.) Nyl
 • *Pertusaria sulcata* Dibben (Kneiper 4312,4313 4352,4422, 4514, 4542)
Pertusaria trachythallina Erichsen
Pertusaria xanthodes Müll. Arg. (Kneiper 4293)
 + *Phaeocalicium polyporaeum* (Nyl.) Tibell
Phaeographis inusta (Ach.) Müll. Arg. (Kneiper 4292)
Phaeophyscia adiastrata (Essl.) Essl. (Kneiper 4503)
Phaeophyscia rubropulchra (Degel.) Essl. (Kneiper 4521)
Physcia adscendens (Fr.) H. Olivier (Kneiper 4414, 4513)
Physcia millegrana Degel. (Kneiper 4309, 4399, 4432, 4440)
 • *Physcia pumilior* R. C. Harris (Kneiper 4463, 4462)
Physcia stellaris (L.) Nyl. (Kneiper 4411)
Placynthiella icmalea (Ach.) Coppins & P. James (Kneiper 4349)

Placynthiella oligotropha (J. R. Laundon) Coppins & P. James (Kneiper 4321, 4407)
Placynthiella uliginosa (Schrader) Coppins & P. James (Kneiper 4526)
Polysporina simplex (Davies) Vězda

- *Porpidia albocaerulescens* (Wulfen) Hertel & Knoph (field id.)
- *Pseudevernia consocians* (Vainio) Hale & Culb. (Kneiper 4330)
- *Psilolechia lucida* (Ach.) M. Choisy (Kneiper 4513)

Punctelia perreticulata (Räsänen) G. Wilh. & Ladd
Punctelia rudecta (Ach.) Krog (Kneiper 4302, 4441)
Pycnothelia papillaria Dufour (Kneiper 4302)

- *Pyrrhospora quernei* (Dickson) Körber (Kneiper 4322, 4340, 4367)

Pyrrhospora varians (Ach.) R. C. Harris (Kneiper 4403)
Ramalina americana Hale (Kneiper 4342)
Ramalina farinacea (L.) Ach. (Kneiper 4344, 4510)

- *Ramalina roesleri* (Hochst. ex Schaerer) Hue *sensu lato* (Kneiper 4379)

Ramalina willeyi R. Howe (Kneiper 4400, 4404, 4405, 4410, 4337, 4343)
Rinodina glauca Ropin
Rinodina maculans Müll. Arg. (Kneiper 4419)

- *Rinodina tephrae* (Tuck.) Herre *sensu lato* (Kneiper 4516)
- *Ropalospora viridis* (Tønsberg) Tønsberg (Kneiper 4351)
- *Scoliciosporum umbrinum* (Ach.) Arnold. (Kneiper 4500)
- **Skyttea radiatilis* (Tuck.) R. Sant., Etayo & Diederich (Kneiper 4452)
- *Thelocarpon laureri* (Flotow) Nyl. (Kneiper 4525)

Trapelia glebulosa (Sm.) J. R. Laundon (Kneiper 4294)
Trapelia placodioides Coppins & P. James (Kneiper 4509)
Trapeliopsis flexuosa (Fr.) Coppins & P. James (Kneiper 4413)

- *Trapeliopsis granulosa* (Hoffm.) Lumbsch. (Kneiper 4484)
- *Tuckermanella fendleri* (Nyl.) Essl. (Kneiper 4355)
- *Usnea cornuta* Körber (Kneiper 4356)

Usnea mutabilis Stirton (Kneiper 4358, 4364, 4389)
Usnea strigosa subsp. *strigosa* (Kneiper 4346, 4367, 4391, 4425)

- *Usnea subfusca* Stirton *sensu lato* (Kneiper 4488)

Usnea subfloridana Stirton

- *Usnea subscabrosa* Nyl. ex Mot. (Kneiper 4357, 4359, 4360, 4361, 4362, 4363, 4366)
- *Usnea trichodea* Ach. (Kneiper 4354, 4363, 4365, 4368, 4369, 4370)

Verrucaria calciseda DC. (Kneiper 4504)
Verrucaria muralis Ach. (Kneiper 4502)

- **Vouauxiella lichenicola* (Lindsay) Petrak & Sydow (Kneiper 4530)

Xanthoparmelia conspersa (Ehrh. ex Ach.) Hale (field id)

- *Xanthoparmelia plittii* (Gyelnik) Hale (Kneiper 4508)

Xanthoria parietina (L.) Th. Fr. (Kneiper 4433)

- *Xylographa opegraphella* Nyl. ex Roth. (4426)

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